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АНАЛИЗ ДИНАМИКИ РАДИАЦИОННОГО ФОНА И РАДИОАКТИВНОГО ЗАГРЯЗНЕНИЯ ТЕРРИТОРИИ ГРОДНЕНСКОЙ ОБЛАСТИ В ПОСТЧЕРНОБЫЛЬСКИЙ ПЕРИОД

Т.И. Зиматкина,

к.б.н., доц.

А.С. Александрович,

к.м.н., доц.,

Гродненский государственный медицинский университет,
г. Гродно, Республика Беларусь

Аннотация: Проведен анализ динамики радиационного фона и радиоактивного загрязнения территории Гродненской области в постчернобыльский период. Результаты проведенного анализа показывают, что на территории Гродненской области к 2020 году наблюдается отрицательная динамика изменения радиоактивного загрязнения. Нами выявлено, что к 2020 году количество населенных пунктов, находящихся под радиационным контролем, значительно уменьшилось. Также установлено, что значительно уменьшилась мощность дозы радионуклидов на данной территории. На сегодняшний день значения радиоактивности в Гродненской области находятся в норме и не представляют особой опасности для жизнедеятельности и здоровья ее населения. Вместе с тем, для дальнейшего контроля радиационной обстановки регулярное проведение радиационного мониторинга остается по-прежнему актуальным.

Ключевые слова: радиация, радиационный фон, радиоактивное загрязнение, радиационный контроль

THE ANALYSIS OF DYNAMICS OF BACKGROUND RADIATION AND RADIOCONTAMINATION OF THE TERRITORY OF THE GRODNO REGION DURING THE POST-CHERNOBYL PERIOD

T.I. Zimatkina,

Ph.D., Assistant Professor

A.S. Aleksandrovich,
Ph.D., Assistant Professor,
Grodno state medical university
Grodno, Republic of Belarus

Annotation: The analysis of dynamics of background radiation and radiocontamination of the territory of the Grodno region is carried out to the post-Chernobyl period. Results of the carried-out analysis show that in the territory of the Grodno region by 2020 negative dynamics of change of radiocontamination is observed. By us it is revealed that by 2020 the number of the settlements which are under radiation control considerably decreased. It is also established that the power of a dose of radionuclides in this territory considerably decreased. Today values of radioactivity are in the Grodno region normal and do not constitute special danger to activity and health of its population. At the same time, for further control of a radiation situation regular carrying out radiation monitoring remains still relevant.

Keywords: radiation, background radiation, radiocontamination, radiation control

Relevance. As a result of explosion on the fourth block of the Chernobyl nuclear power plant on April 26, 1986 the territory of our country was intensively polluted by the radioactive isotopes released into the atmosphere. In spite of the fact that there passed thirty-five years, it is impossible to think of it, as of the event, which consigned to the past [1, 2].

Accident, unprecedented on the scales, on the Chernobyl nuclear power plant caused attraction to overcoming its medical consequences about 2000 doctors, 4000 people of average medical personnel and more than 1200 students of older years of medical institutes [1, 2]. 230 temporary laboratory and dosimetric mobile crews, more than 400 medical crews were created, 125 special cars are allocated.

Pollution by radionuclides tseziy137 over 37 kBq/sq.m occurred on 57,900 sq.km, or 0.5 % of the total area of the Russian Federation, 46 500 of sq.km, or 23 % of the territory of Republic of Belarus, and 41,900 sq.km or 4.8 % of the territory of Ukraine [1, 3-5].

Features of weather conditions during the period from April 26 to May 10, 1986 and the structure and dynamics of emergency emission of radioactive materials caused the difficult nature of pollution of the territory of our country.

In the territory of our country polluted by long-living radionuclides now more than one and a half million people from whom third – children and teenagers aged till 17 years old [1, 3] live in 2906 settlements. Radiocontamination of the territory continues to affect negatively the state of health of people and can lead to growth of incidence, earlier mortality and an invalidism, including, from oncological diseases.

The main radiological consequences of accident on nuclear power plants are distributed on early and remote. Carry to early consequences of accidents: acute radial illness, local injuries of skin, eye; hematologic, immunological, cytogenetic disturbances at liquidators of consequences of accident and the population. The remote radiological consequences are: growth of cancer cases of a thyroid gland and leukemia, increase in frequency of crayfish at liquidators, separate forms of solid crayfish at the population, growth of the general incidence and mortality of the population and liquidators of consequences of accident.

The Grodno region also to treat the areas polluted by radiation. Today the analysis of dynamics of background radiation and radiocontamination of this territory plays an important role as here the most dangerous radiation object of Republic of Belarus – the Ostrovetskaya NPP is located.

Purpose. The analysis of dynamics of background radiation and radiocontamination of the territory of the Grodno region during the post-Chernobyl period.

Materials and methods of a research. As materials of the population served official statistical data of the Grodno regional center of hygiene, epidemiology and public health and the Republican center for hydrometeorology, control of radiocontamination and monitoring of the environment [4-6]. In work epidemiological, comparative and estimated and statistical methods of researches are applied.

Results and their discussion. It is established that at explosion of the Chernobyl NPP 10 EBk of radioactive materials, including 6.3 EBk of noble gases came to the environment [1]. 50-60 % of iodine and 30-36 % of cesium, which are contained in the reactor, were thrown out. As a result of damp and dry rainfall on the territory about 2/3 radioactive materials dropped out.

The main contribution to pollution of the environment and forming of dose loads of the population rendered cesium¹³⁷, rutenium¹⁰⁷, strontsium⁹⁰, plutonium²³⁸, plutonium²³⁹, plutonium²⁴⁰, tsezium¹³⁴, iodine¹³¹, iodine¹³², iodine¹³³, iodine¹³⁵, neptunium²³⁹, molibdenum⁹⁹, barium¹⁴⁰, strontsium⁸⁹ and about 25 more radionuclides with short half-lives. Cleaning of the territory of

Republic of Belarus of radioactive cesium and strontium requires 300 years, i.e. 10 half-lives of these elements.

It is revealed that the total area of zones with pollution level cesium¹³⁷ 15 Ki/sq.km is more than 10 thousand sq.km more (about 6400 sq.km in Belarus). In total in the territory of this zone, about 640 settlements (116 thousand people) are located. Including in the territory of the Grodno region 84 settlements with periodic radiation control where pollution density tseziyem¹³⁷ from 1 to 5 Ki/sq.km, including in Novogrudsky district – 12, in Iyevsky – 50, in Dyatlovsky – 22 settlements were polluted. According to 2019, the number of settlements did not change.

Distribution of these substances plays an important role in development of various diseases. Therefore, in our country the state of environment is actively controlled. Special points of observation, which fix certain indicators for assessment of radiocontamination of atmospheric air, water and the soil, were created. The values characterizing radioactivity are the power of a dose of gamma radiation and total beta activity of natural atmospheric losses. The main points of observation in the Grodno region are located in the cities of Volkovysk and Lida. The territorial centers of hygiene and epidemiology take daily measurement of power of gamma radiation in control points of reperny network.

It is shown based on results of the gamma and spectrometer analysis in 2005-2009 that in tests of aerosols natural radionuclides were identified: berillium⁷, kalium⁴⁰, plumbum²¹⁰. The total beta activity of these substances in 2006 equaled $13,54 \cdot 10^{-5}$ Bq/m³.

According to the resolution of Council of ministers of Republic of Belarus of 11.01.2016 No. 9 "About the approval of the list of the settlements and objects which are in radiocontamination zones" in the territory of the Grodno region in an accommodation zone with periodic radiation control in the territory with a pollution density cesium¹³⁷ from 1 to 5 Ki/sq.km 84 settlements, including in Iyevsky district – 50, Dyatlovsky – 22, Novogrudsky – 11 are located [4]. One of the most polluted areas of the Grodno region is Iyevsky district. In 2012 the power of a dose of gamma radiation was equal to 12.2 μSv/h; 2013 – 12.1 μSv/h; 2014 – 11.9 μSv/h; 2015 – 12.1 μSv/h; 2016 – 11.4 μSv/h; 2017 – 12.0 μSv/h; 2018 – 13.0 μSv/h; 2019 – 11.8 μSv/h.

It is established that in 2019 contents berillium⁷ in atmospheric air on points of observation was in range from $725 \cdot 10^{-6}$ Bq/m³ up to $6192 \cdot 10^{-6}$ Bq/m³, plumbum²¹⁰ – from $28.0 \cdot 10^{-6}$ Bq/m³ to $859.0 \cdot 10^{-6}$ Bq/m³. The highest activities berillium⁷ are characteristic of warm months with higher solar

radiation. The peak of volume activity plumbum²¹⁰ on many points of observation in 2019 fell on November.

Averages for the 4th quarter 2020 of value of power of a dose of gamma radiation in points of observations of the Grodno region did not exceed 0.10 $\mu\text{Sv/h}$ [6]. During the period from October to December, 2020 average values of total beta activity of natural radioactive losses from a ground layer of the atmosphere corresponded to the established long-term values. Therefore, also special changes within a year did not happen.

Conclusions. Results of the carried-out analysis show that in the territory of the Grodno region by 2020 negative dynamics of change of radiocontamination is observed. By us it is revealed that by 2020 the number of the settlements which are under radiation control considerably decreased. It is also established that the power of a dose of radionuclides in this territory considerably decreased. Today values of radioactivity are in the Grodno region normal and do not constitute special danger to activity and health of its population. At the same time, for further control of a radiation situation regular carrying out radiation monitoring remains still relevant.

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